

Grain yield stability of individual cereal-legume mixtures grown across Europe

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Summary

Mixed cultivation of two or more crop species on the same piece of land at a given time may enhance crop yield stability. We assessed yield stability by first calculating the expected coefficients of variance (CV%) for cereal-legume mixtures grown across contrasting environments based on the corresponding yield variation of the mixture components grown separately in pure cultures; and then dividing the expected CV% by the observed CV% for each mixture. The ratio between the expected and observed CV% is the stability index, with values >1 indicating greater stability of the mixed crops and values <1 indicating greater stability of the crops grown separately. Stability indices for eight out of 11 barley/pea and wheat/faba bean mixtures grown across Europe were between 0.7 and 1.8 (mean 1.0), whilst two barley/pea mixtures had indices >3.7. The results are relevant in the discussion of crop mixtures as means to increase yield stability.

Key words: Barley, diversification, faba bean, pea, wheat, yield stability, intercropping

Introduction

The mixed cultivation of two or more species on the same piece of land is considered to bring a planned diversity of species and varieties into agricultural landscapes, which in turn could enhance yield stability and food security (Frison *et al.*, 2011). The yield stabilising effect could be caused by two different crop species being adapted to (slightly) different environmental conditions, making them differently responsive or sensitive to management actions, weather extremes, etc. For example, if one mixture component suffers more than the other from a disease or extreme weather, the other component in a mixture could partly compensate for the corresponding yield losses by utilising more of the available resources. The yield stabilising effect has been investigated frequently in field experiments, but results are conflicting (Pelzer *et al.*, 2014; Raseduzzaman & Jensen, 2017; Yu *et al.*, 2016). Evidence for increased stability in mixtures is often obtained from the comparison of coefficients of variance (CV%) for mean yields assessed in mixed vs pure cultures (e.g. Raseduzzaman & Jensen, 2017). Comparisons based on CV% are appropriate only if the yield mean and standard deviation vary in a parallel way; otherwise a bias would happen, whereby high means result in low CV% and low means in high CV%. Suitable alternative variability measures

not influenced by the mean value include the variance (Haughey *et al.*, 2018). Further to the issue of variability (or stability) measure, there could be arithmetic reasons linking the variability seen in the pure cultures of mixture components grown in contrasting environments, and the emerging variability that would be expected for their mixtures grown in the same environments. There is apparently a need to identify suitable approaches for evaluating yield stability in crop mixtures grown in contrasting environments including those that support both high and low yields (Temesgen *et al.*, 2015). As a part of the EU-funded Horizon2020 project DIVERSify (www.plant-teams.eu), various cereal-legume mixtures were grown in field trials under different nutrient treatments across contrasting environments in Europe (Karley *et al.*, 2018), and the yield data obtained are suitable to explore the hypothesis that mixtures enhance yield stability compared to the pure culture of the mixture components. The objectives of the paper were to (i) develop an approach for the comparison of yield variabilities (and thus yield stability) across contrasting environments; and (ii) apply that approach to a limited data set from 11 individual cereal-legume (barley & pea and wheat & faba bean) mixtures grown across Europe (Sweden, Denmark, Scotland, Germany, Italy) under partly different fertilization conditions.

Materials and Methods

Experimental sites

Data from five experimental field trials grown across Europe during the same year (2018) were used for the analyses (Table 1). Compared to long-term average temperature and precipitation sums, the weather during the investigated 2018 growing season was warmer and drier in some locations, but cooler and wetter in other locations.

Table 1. *Overview of the experimental cereal-legume trials grown across Europe in 2018 and used in the analyses. Sowing densities are given separately for barley/pea (BP) and wheat/faba bean (WF) pure cultures and mixtures. Mean temperatures and precipitation sums refer to the individual cultivation periods of the five trials*

Location	Latitude, longitude	Fertiliser* treatments (kg N ha ⁻¹)	Cultivation period (2018)	Sowing densities** (seeds m ⁻²)	Mean temp. (°C) [§]	Precip. sum (mm) [§]	Days with precip. >1 mm
Ancona (Italy)	43° 32' 42" N 13° 21' 34" E	Two (40, 80)	1 Feb–16 Jul	BP 350/80	14.31 (15.0) ¹	557 (328) ¹	25
Dundee (UK)	56° 48' 17" N 3° 11' 17" E	One (0)	2 Apr–3 Sep	BP 360/80 WF 440/50	13.0 (n/a)	211 (249) ²	36
Münster (Germany)	51° 58' 32" N 7° 33' 59" E	Two (0, 70)	23 Apr–11 Aug	BP 360/80 WF 440/40	17.9 (15.4) ¹	173 (231) ¹	n/a
Taastrup (Denmark)	56° 40' 7" N 12° 18' 20" E	Two (23, 65)	19 Apr–15 Sep	BP 360/70 WF 528/48	17.8 (n/a)	119 (n/a)	24
Uppsala (Sweden)	59° 50' 6" N 15° 42' 0" E	Two (0, 140)	30 Apr–6 Sep	BP 400/90 WF 490/60	17.8 (14.4) ³	178 (220) ³	18

* Fertilisers were applied as commercial NPK fertilisers

** Values indicate sowing densities in the pure cultures, and the corresponding values in the intercrops were 50 % of the values in the pure cultures using replacement designs in all trials

§ The values in parentheses indicate long-term means; ¹1990–2020, ²1971–2000, ³1950–2019. (n/a) not available

Varietal and mixture information

Various spring-sown varieties of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) and faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) were grown in pure and mixed cultures in the five experimental trials located across Europe. Not all varieties and mixtures were grown in all locations, but all mixtures (and the corresponding pure cultures) considered in this investigation were grown in at least two different locations (Table 2).

Table 2. Overview of the varieties grown as pure and mixed cultures across Europe in 2018 and used in the analyses. Variety acronyms: Ald 'KWS Alderon', Box 'Boxer', Cla 'Clara', Cor 'Cornetto', Fue 'Fuego', Har 'Hardy', Ing 'Ingrid', Pla 'RGT Planet', Sal 'Salome', Tam 'Tamtam', Tea 'Tea', Tyb 'Tybalt'; n/a not applicable

Location	Barley/pea	Wheat/faba bean
Ancona (Italy)	Tea-Har	n/a
Dundee (UK)	Pla-Ing, Pla-Cla, Tam-Ing, Tam-Cla	Tyb-Fue
Münster (Germany)	Sal-Har	Cor-Fue, Tyb-Fue
Taastrup (Denmark)	Pla-Ing, Tam-Ing, Tea-Har, Sal-Har	Cor-Box, Cor-Fue, Ald-Box, Ald-Fue
Uppsala (Sweden)	Pla-Ing, Pla-Cla, Tam-Ing, Tam-Cla	Cor-Box, Cor-Fue, Ald-Box, Ald-Fue

Assessments of grain yields

Agronomic grain yields (Mg ha⁻¹) were assessed in plots of between 1 and 12 m² using combine harvesters.

Analysis of grain yield stability – theory

Yield stability in cropping systems can be assessed with different statistical methods and it is often advisable to use more than one stability (or variability) measure (Mead & Riley, 1981; Piepho, 1998; Temesgen *et al.*, 2015). However, evidence for increased stability in mixtures is often claimed based on the comparison of coefficients of variance (CV%) for mean yields assessed in mixed *vs* pure cultures (Raseduzzaman & Jensen, 2017). Apart from the issue that the CV% is influenced by both the mean and variability, this approach is problematic also because the variability of mean yields in mixtures can be expected to be lower than the corresponding pure cultures simply for arithmetic reasons. The numeric example in Table 3 illustrates this arithmetic relationship: The admixing of two contrasting components ameliorates the extreme values observed for the mixture components when they are grown separately in pure cultures even when no biological effect is invoked.

Analysis of grain yield stability – application

We assessed yield stability by first calculating the expected CV% for individual cereal-legume mixtures grown across contrasting environments based on the corresponding yield variation of the mixture components grown separately in pure cultures; and then dividing the expected CV% for each mixture by the corresponding observed CV%:

$$\text{Stability index} = \text{Expected CV\%} / \text{Observed CV\%},$$

with values >1 indicating greater stability (or smaller variability) of the mixed crops and values <1 indicating greater stability of the pure crops grown separately. In addition to the CV%, we also evaluated the corresponding expected and observed variances, which enabled us to statistically test whether observed variances were different from expected variances using Levene's test of equal variances performed on log-transformed data according to Piepho (1998). All statistics were calculated using SPSS (version 26).

Table 3. *Numeric example illustrating the expected variability of mean yields in mixtures based on the yield values assessed in the corresponding pure cultures. The example shows 10 arbitrary observations (e.g. from different cultivation environments or years) of grain yield values (Mg ha⁻¹) of a crop A and B grown in pure cultures and the corresponding total yields that are expected when growing the same crops in a 50:50 mixture in a replacement design and assuming the same yields per area in the pure and mixed cultures (i.e. the total expected yield in a mixture is calculated as the mean of the yields achieved in the two pure cultures). The upper part of the table shows the yield values for the 10 observations, whilst the lower part shows various descriptive measures for the crops A and B grown in pure and mixed cultures*

Observation	Pure culture A	Pure culture B	Mixture A & B
1	15	8	11.5
2	9	11	10
3	13	6	9.5
4	6	9	7.5
5	10	4	7
6	4	7	5.5
7	12	5	8.5
8	10	12	11
9	8	3	5.5
10	8	10	9
Mean	9.5	7.5	8.5
Standard deviation	3.28	3.03	2.11
Coefficient of variance (CV%)	34.5	40.4	24.8
Variance	10.7	9.2	4.4

Results

The stability indices for eight out of 11 individual mixtures were between 0.7 and 1.8 (mean 1.0), whilst two individual barley/pea mixtures had indices >3, indicating strongly enhanced stability in the mixed crops compared to the mixture components grown separately (Table 4). The legume component of these two mixtures, grown in Sweden and Scotland, was the same in both cases (pea ‘Clara’) and appeared to carry a yield stabilising effect. However, these two barley/pea mixtures with the highest stability indices were also the ones with the lowest yields among all 10 mixtures investigated here.

Fig. 1. Observed vs expected variances for 11 individual cereal-legume mixtures grown in various environments across Europe. The broken line indicates where observed variances = expected variances. Wheat/faba bean mixtures are underlined, whilst barley/pea mixtures are not. *ALL* indicates the variances across all mixtures. The variety acronyms are shown in Table 2, and the source data are in Table 4.

The comparison of expected and observed variances showed the same pattern as for the CV% (Table 4). Indeed, most of the mixtures showed increased observed variance (in mixtures) compared to the expected variance from the pure cultures of their components, indicating decreased stability of the mixtures (Fig. 1). However, Levene's test of equal variances indicated only few cases of significantly different variances, i.e. increased stability of the two barley/pea mixtures including the pea 'Clara'.

Discussion

The preliminary analysis of the data suggests that the approach chosen here is promising because it combines different variability measures in a similar way as also others have done (Temesgen *et al.*, 2015). Measures based on CV% only are problematic because its value is influenced by both the mean and variance, and the additional use of other measures such as the variance is preferable not least because the equality of variances can easily be tested statistically (Piepho, 1998; Haughey *et al.*, 2018). The stability index proposed here was calculated as the ratio between the expected (from pure cultures) and observed (in the mixtures) CV%. This index is probably a much less biased measure in most cases than the CV%, because the yield levels are similar for the observed and expected data set, implying that a strong bias due to different yield levels is less likely in our stability index than the CV% alone.

Instead of a primary focus on genotype-environment interaction mechanisms, our approach adopts a farm perspective in terms of risk and cropping security (Mead & Riley, 1981). Thus, a farmer's interest for mixtures would increase only if this farming system supplied him with more stable yields in adverse conditions compared to growing the mixture components separately in pure cultures; i.e. the farmer does not mind if the crops are produced as mixed or pure crops on the same farm.

Table 4. *Expected (from pure cultures) and observed yields, variances and coefficients of variance (CV%), together with the corresponding stability indices (exp. CV%/obs. CV%) and P values from Levene's test of equal variances (significant P values in bold) for 11 individual cereal-legume mixtures grown in various environments across Europe. N indicates the total number of locations and fertilizer treatments (for details see Table 1) for each mixture. The first six mixtures represent barley/pea, the rest wheat/faba bean mixtures*

Mixture	N	Exp. mean	Exp. variance	Exp. CV%	Obs. mean	Obs. variance	Obs. CV%	Stability index	Levene's test
RGT Planet & Ingrid	5	2.83	1.69	45.9	3.33	2.67	49.2	0.93	0.695
RGT Planet & Clara	3	1.64	0.33	35.2	1.68	0.01	1.8	19.69	0.020
Tamtam & Ingrid	5	2.83	1.59	44.5	3.19	2.16	46.1	0.97	0.826
Tamtam & Clara	3	1.70	0.37	35.6	1.91	0.03	9.5	3.74	0.050
Tea & Hardy	4	2.97	0.51	24.0	3.38	0.61	23.2	1.04	0.936
Salome & Hardy	4	2.61	1.61	48.7	3.99	2.08	36.2	1.35	0.676
Cornetto & Boxer	4	3.58	0.46	19.0	4.27	1.45	28.2	0.68	0.772
Cornetto & Fuego	6	3.62	0.78	24.4	3.99	1.19	27.3	0.89	0.963
KWS Alderon & Fuego	3	3.90	0.44	17.0	4.56	1.36	25.6	0.66	0.348
KWS Alderon & Boxer	4	3.57	0.28	14.9	4.53	0.93	21.3	0.70	0.632
Tybalt & Fuego	3	2.49	3.85	78.8	3.14	1.95	44.5	1.77	0.444
All	44	2.96	1.28	38.3	3.52	1.82	38.3	1.00	0.836

The preliminary data set available for this analysis included too few different environments and did not allow a rigorous test of the stability hypothesis (Frison *et al.*, 2011). However, the stability index in combination with testing the equality of variances is promising as this combined approach allows for both clear graphical visualisation and statistical testing. The stability hypothesis was here explored only in terms of spatial variability, i.e. stability across different environments, although it might be more interesting to test this hypothesis using data from different environments and years (e.g. extreme weather) to also assess temporal stability (Pelzer *et al.*, 2014; Raseduzzaman & Jensen, 2017; Yu *et al.*, 2016). The proposed approach is suitable to analyse data regarding both spatial and temporal variability. In our preliminary analysis, we found only two mixtures conferring statistical evidence for greater yield stability in the mixtures compared to the expected value derived from the variability in the pure cultures of the mixture components. The legume component of these two mixtures, grown in Sweden (Uppsala) and Scotland (Dundee), was the same in both mixtures (pea 'Clara'). However, these two barley/pea mixtures, with the highest stability indices, were also the mixtures with the lowest yields among all 10 mixtures investigated here. It will be interesting to see whether this pattern emerges also in a broader analysis including data from different environments and years with contrasting weather, which are available in the DIVERSify project. The analysis of the broader data set, using the approach proposed here and other methods (Piepho, 1998; Temesgen *et al.*, 2015), will enable a more robust evaluation regarding the use of crop mixtures as means to increase yield stability in a farm perspective, i.e. in terms of farming risk and cropping security.

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